

Developing a Corpus of Syntactically-Annotated Learner Language for English

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Abstract

Syntactic annotation for learner language has received some attention in recent years. We review the SALLE annotation scheme for syntactically annotating learner English, the main effort we are aware of that thoroughly investigates the linguistic categories for annotating syntax, presenting an overview of its development. Specifically, we focus on what is entailed in designing and implementing such a scheme with respect to: 1) interpretation, 2) defining the syntactic dependency layers, and 3) handling challenging cases.

1 Introduction

Syntactic annotation of data for second language learners is in its infancy, with only a handful of projects considering it and most focusing on improving automatic analysis [1, 6, 10, 14, 19, 20]. We focus on the SALLE (Syntactically Annotating the Language of Learner English) project, the main effort we are aware of that investigates the linguistic categories for annotating syntax. The SALLE project had its first publication at TLT in 2009 [3], and we review what has transpired since then [15], pointing towards further syntactic analysis of learner data.

As learner data can diverge from canonical language use, the annotation scheme splits annotation into separate layers, one for each piece of linguistic evidence. This can be illustrated with part-of-speech (POS) annotation [2]: in the phrase *for almost every jobs nowadays* [2], the word *jobs* is distributionally in a singular noun slot, but has the English plural marker. SALLE thus annotates two different POS.

This under-committal to an analysis is argued to be appropriate for second language research [16] and is applicable for canonical or non-canonical constructions, but there is a question of the degree of interpretation needed to annotate learner data [21]. In this short paper, we sketch: a) how interpretation is handled; b) how the syntactic dependency layers are defined; and c) examples revealing difficulty in annotating. The goal is not to present a large corpus or argue for particular analyses, but to outline some crucial decisions we found in designing and implementing a

syntactic annotation scheme for learner language. We can only make the reader aware of the major issues here; many more details are available in our previous publications; in a beta version of the annotation guidelines [5]; and in a recently-completed dissertation thesis [15]. A take-home point is an old one [cf., e.g., 22]: compared to the quirks of the text itself, the ease or difficulty of annotation lies as much, if not more, in the clarity and ease of the annotation scheme, in the quality of the guidelines, and in providing a decision procedure for “corner cases.”

2 Interpretation

To discuss interpreting learner data, our perspective needs to be established. In SALLE, the goal is to be able to annotate any level of learner from any native language (L1) for any type of text. This means that little is assumed about the learner or the context in which something was written [compare to 13]. This leads to a second point: the annotation tries to avoid intended meaning, a point which fits with the goal of annotating categories in the learner data that benefit second language research [16]. Indeed, the annotation is not focused on errors or target hypotheses [12]—although, mismatches arising from different linguistic layers may point towards non-canonical structures (see section 3).

Additionally, while dependencies are often used to index meaning, the goal for SALLE is to annotate as much about the syntax as possible; when the syntactic form does not correspond to a likely semantic interpretation, one nonetheless annotates the apparent syntactic properties (more below). Finally, the project subscribes to the notion that all annotation is interpretation [11], and a thorough set of guidelines are used to adjudicate complicated cases, e.g., whether to “attach high” (sec. 4.1 of [5]), how to handle sentences lacking a copula (sec. 5.1.1 of [5]), etc.

The principles laid out in the annotator guidelines (of which we focus on the first two) shed light on how the different goals play out. The first principle is ‘Give the learner the benefit of the doubt’ and the second is to ‘Assume as little as possible about the intended meaning of the learner’ (p. 3 of [5]).

Benefit of the Doubt Giving the benefit of the doubt means assuming that the text is more well-formed than not. More specifically, this means trying to fit the sentence into the context, if possible, and, if not possible, to annotate as if the sentence were as syntactically well-formed as it can be, possibly ignoring meaning.

Consider the sentence *Cause all over the nation use it .*, occurring after *English skill is important*. In this case, the intended meaning may be something along the lines of *(because) all over the nation people use it*, but to annotate this way requires positing a missing word (*people*). Aside from the context not providing enough evidence of one intended meaning or another, this analysis presumes an error. The fallback strategy is to annotate the sentence in a more well-formed way, staying relatively within the bounds of the context. We see in figure 1 that this means treating *all* as the subject (SUBJ). (In either analysis, *cause* is an un-

selected complementizer (CPZR)—i.e., the subcategorization frame of *use* is not <CPZR,SUBJ,OBJ>—an issue stemming from sentence segmentation.) Crucially, the analysis based on a preferred intended form is ignored.

Figure 1: Giving the learner the benefit of the doubt

Semantics Eschewing (intended) semantic form was illustrated above, but to take a perhaps clearer example: regarding *then, I study law degree .*, one does not usually study degrees. However, *study* takes a noun object, so *degree* (cf. *degree*) serves as the object, and the only oddity is in requiring a determiner (see section 3 for subcategorization). The point is that, across a variety of contexts and learners, meaning cannot always be determined, whereas syntactic properties often can.

Being less concerned about intended meaning also means that we ignore some properties that may be deemed non-nativelike. If there is an unusual word choice or a pragmatically-odd construction, for example, where the sentence is syntactically well-formed, it will be annotated as if there are no problems (cf. the principle of minimal interaction [8]). In (1), for instance, the phrase *in each one of the spaces* may sound odd, but syntactically it is a valid prepositional phrase and is annotated as such. Thus, an annotator does not need to determine the source of the unacceptability of a sentence.

- (1) In this moment of my life, I have different goals in each one of the spaces.

3 Distinct but Intertwined Layers

The original intention of SALLE was to provide multiple syntactic dependency layers, corresponding to different kinds of evidence [4, 15, 17]: 1) subcategorization, 2) morphological dependencies, and 3) distributional dependencies. Subcategorization and morphologically-based dependencies, however, require some degree of context to define, and thus make distributional dependencies rather redundant [17]. That is, while the motivation for learner language is to keep the layers somewhat distinct, they cannot be kept totally distinct if annotation is to be practical (cf. also, [9]). We walk through the arguments from [17].

Subcategorization Although subcategorization is not often a part of syntactic annotation, it helps capture argument structure innovations [4]. Consider *we moved*

again to other house, where *house* requires a determiner. SALLE captures this by having *house* subcategorize for a determiner (<DET>), despite none being present.

For words with more than one possible subcategorization frame (e.g., plural nouns), all of them could be annotated, but this would not capture cases where a reading is prohibited. Thus, context is used to annotate only one frame, i.e., *distributional information* disambiguates subcategorization. In fact, subcategorization annotation often is preferred over distributional dependencies. Consider (2).

(2) I wondered what success **to be**.

Morphologically, *to be* has non-finite marking and the clause is thus a non-finite complement (XCOMP), as in the left side of figure 2. With a subcategorization for a finite complement (COMP), there is a mismatch. In a distributional tree, COMP is the label, but the subtree is unclear (see right side). If *to be* is in a finite distributional position, is *to* a finite auxiliary with a verbal complement? Is *be* a finite verb with an extraneous *to*? Subcategorization does not force an internal analysis.

Figure 2: Morph. (left) and dist. (right) trees for a complement mismatch

Likewise, for missing arguments, annotating subcategorization information captures differences that (distributional) dependencies alone cannot capture.

Morphosyntax Consider annotating dependency trees based strictly on morphological forms. For (2) and depending on the annotation scheme, this would mean annotating based on *wondered* being either a past tense verb (VVD) or a past participle (VVN), *what* as a determiner (DDQ) or pronoun (also DDQ, but a different syntactic function), and *to* as a preposition (II) or a infinitive marker (TO). This would lead to 8 ($=2 \times 2 \times 2$) different trees, many of which are hard to define (e.g., *to* as II) or completely irrelevant for what was produced (e.g., *wondered* as VVN).

As with subcategorization, we annotate the closest fit to the context, where the “closest fit” generally leads to the most well-formed tree (section 2). For example, in *the step of my walked*, *walked* is marked as VVN, not VVD, as VVN is a tag for adjectival uses, and thus, in this nominal context, leads to a better tree. The ultimate decision in SALLE is to annotate morphosyntactic dependencies and subcategorization, but not dependencies rooted mainly in distributional evidence. Essentially, while other information is used (e.g., context), the annotation is primarily based on *form*. This allows the annotation to be applied to data from different kinds of learners and texts: one may use unspecified annotations at times (e.g., for extraneous words), but it is relatively clear which POS categories one starts with. Additionally, from the NLP perspective, there are some initial indications that basing the annotation on form could lead to better parsing results [see 19].

4 Some Challenging Cases

Consider (3), where the words *heart* and *accoss* present challenges in interpreting what words are being used. SALLE has a guideline of treating a word like its intended spelling when a misspelling is “phonetically or typographically-driven (but not semantically-driven)” [5, p. 20]. While there are debatable cases, the general idea is to balance the idea of giving the learner the benefit of the doubt—when it is clear to do so—and using the evidence (i.e., form) at hand.

(3) I can **heart** the sound of stream **accoss** the stone.

In this case, the fact that *accoss* is similar to *across* allows it to be treated like the preposition. As for *heart*, however, due to the fact that *heart* is an actual word, SALLE deems it too unclear as to whether it is a misspelling to treat it like *hear*. Thus, one winds up with a tree where the noun *heart* is an unspecified dependent of *can*, with an unspecified dependent *sound*, as in figure 3. The “minor” judgment of what constitutes an acceptable misspelling turns out to have big consequences [see 15, p.214 for more discussion of this example].

Figure 3: Example of a problematic lemma

In addition to revealing the impact of deciding on which word is present, the SALLE scheme has also provided some insight into how to treat coordination [4] and promises to provide other insights into dependencies for learner data. More to the point for this paper, the scheme allows one to provide informative annotation without guessing at the exact intention. For example, the meaning is unclear in figure 4. Nonetheless, giving the learner the benefit of the doubt, most of the syntactic properties can be determined, as shown. Aside from an unspecified () relation between *felt* and *me*, the tree is well-formed (see sec. 6.6 of [5] for more).

Figure 4: Unclear meaning/intention with syntactic annotation

5 Conclusion and Outlook

We have reviewed the SALLE annotation scheme for syntactically annotating learner English, an annotation effort that has aimed to thoroughly investigate the linguistic categories for annotating syntax. Specifically, we have focused on the design and implementation of the scheme with respect to: 1) interpretation, 2) definition of the syntactic dependency layers, and 3) the treatment of challenging cases. While many challenges remain for syntactic annotation, we have uncovered many issues facing linguistic annotation for second language data, such as: the importance of thoroughly defining a word, the need for separation between morphology and distribution and yet the interrelatedness of the two, and the lasting effect of what seem like simple heuristics onto all aspects of the annotation.

One major benefit of the SALLE scheme, as the first of its kind, stems from the fact that it is thoroughly documented; as we state on our website¹: “The decisions we have made (certainly needing refinement in some cases) point out many of the essential questions that need to be addressed for linguistically annotating learner data, and we hope they can stimulate discussion.” Outlining our decisions and the reasons for them should help pave the way for future work, where the decisions researchers make may be quite different. Given that annotation provides linguistic interpretation, a user of the annotation is able to understand what it means and what it does not mean. Indeed, an inter-annotator agreement study covering the different annotation layers reported fairly high inter-annotator agreement [18]. The difficulty of the text—whether stemming from complicated linguistic patterns or from innovative constructions—had an impact on agreement statistics, but the scheme has been successfully applied to learners of different levels and native languages.

Aside from continuing to apply the annotation to new and varied data, there are many routes to take this work: 1) automatically parse more data, determining how parsing can be improved [19]; 2) extract information relevant for second language acquisition (SLA) investigations; 3) thoroughly compare the positives and negatives of this scheme to more semantically-oriented annotation schemes [e.g., 6]; 4) continue to unpack specific linguistic constructions (e.g., coordination [4]), to see which aspects of the annotation are learner-specific or not; and 5) connect the work to other non-canonical data, such as historical texts and web data [7].

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